

The Origins of Major World Religions¹

Partha Majumdar
Kalinga University, Raipur, Chhattisgarh
Partha.majumdar@hotmail.com

Abstract

The origins of the world's major religions—Buddhism, Judaism, Christianity, Islam, Sikhism, and Hinduism—are deeply intertwined with their respective cultural, social, and historical contexts. This article explores the evolution of these faiths, tracing Buddhism's reformation from Hinduism, Judaism's covenant with God, Christianity's rise from Roman oppression, Islam's revelations through the Prophet Muhammad, Sikhism's synthesis of Hindu and Islamic traditions, and Hinduism's deep roots in the Indian subcontinent. By examining their foundational stories and core teachings, this article highlights the unique paths each religion has taken and their profound impact on shaping human history and culture.

¹ My thoughts are written by OpenAI ChatGPT-4o.

Introduction

Religions have played an integral role in shaping civilisations, fostering cultures, and providing a moral compass to countless societies throughout history. Each major world religion has emerged from distinct historical, social, and spiritual contexts, reflecting how humans have sought meaning, purpose, and connection to the divine. The major world religions—Buddhism, Judaism, Christianity, Islam, Sikhism, and Hinduism—offer unique perspectives on the nature of existence, human suffering, the divine, and the ultimate purpose of life. They have guided civilisations through peace and conflict, influencing law, art, ethics, and human rights while addressing questions about mortality, justice, and salvation.

Understanding the origins and evolution of these religions sheds light on their profound impact on shaping the world’s spiritual, philosophical, and social frameworks. While distinct in its core teachings and practices, each religion shares common threads of seeking truth, offering moral guidance, and fostering communal identity. These shared aspirations and their unique theological perspectives contribute to our vast religious diversity.

This article explores the foundational stories of these six major religions, analysing the conditions that led to their formation, their core teachings, and how they have transformed over time. Buddhism emerged as a reformation of Hinduism, critiquing the caste system and ritualism, while Judaism arose from a covenant between God and Abraham, offering the first major monotheistic worldview. Christianity evolved from a Jewish sect into a global religion based on the teachings of Jesus Christ. At the same time, Islam, born in the Arabian Peninsula, introduced a new revelation through Prophet Muhammad. Sikhism, drawing from both Hindu and Islamic elements, emerged as a distinct religion promoting equality and justice. Hinduism, the world’s oldest religion, developed over millennia through the absorption of diverse philosophical and spiritual influences.

By tracing these origins, this article aims to offer insights into the enduring influence of these religions, their role in shaping human history, and how they continue to guide the spiritual journeys of billions of people worldwide.

Buddhism: A Reformation from Hinduism

Buddhism, founded by Siddhartha Gautama (later known as the Buddha) around the 6th century BCE, arose during significant social and religious upheaval in India. Siddhartha was born into a noble family of the Shakya clan in Lumbini, in present-day Nepal. He was raised in the traditions of Hinduism, the predominant religious system of the time. This period saw a rigid caste system, with Brahmins (the priestly caste) exercising significant control over religious and social life. Rituals, sacrifices, and interpreting sacred texts (the Vedas) were largely confined to the Brahmin class, leading to social stratification and exclusion.

The Buddha's Journey: A Departure from Vedic Norms

Siddhartha's early life was one of luxury. Still, his eventual exposure to the realities of human suffering—old age, sickness, and death—prompted him to seek answers beyond the rituals and caste restrictions of the Vedic tradition. He renounced his princely life in search of spiritual liberation and enlightenment. After years of asceticism and meditation, he attained *Nirvana* (spiritual enlightenment) under the Bodhi tree in Bodh Gaya.

Buddhism's origin partly critiqued certain aspects of Hindu society, particularly the caste system and the Brahminical monopoly on religious practices. While Siddhartha retained several core philosophical elements from the Vedic tradition—such as *karma* (the law of moral causation), *dharma* (ethical duty), and *samsara* (the cycle of rebirth)—his teachings presented a significant departure from the Hindu concepts of *Brahman* (the ultimate, formless reality) and *atman* (the soul or self).

Key Philosophical Distinctions between Buddhism and Hinduism

1. **Caste System:** Hindu society was (and still is, in some ways) stratified into four main castes—Brahmins, Kshatriyas, Vaishyas, and Shudras. Each caste had specific duties and responsibilities, with the Brahmins occupying the highest position in religious matters. Troubled by the inequalities perpetuated by this system, Siddhartha advocated for a casteless society where all individuals could work toward their spiritual liberation, regardless of birth status. Buddhism, therefore, promotes *sangha* (community) based on spiritual merit rather than social class.
2. **No Supreme Creator God:** While Hinduism espouses belief in *Brahman*—a formless, infinite, and eternal supreme reality that manifests in various deities—Buddhism does not affirm the existence of a creator god. The Buddha refrained from theological debates about the divine, focusing instead on the practical path

to end human suffering through self-effort and wisdom. The Buddha's teachings emphasised a *nontheistic* approach to spirituality, where individuals are responsible for their liberation (through the Eightfold Path) rather than relying on divine intervention.

3. **No Permanent Self (Anatta):** One of Buddhism's most revolutionary ideas is the doctrine of *anatta* (non-self), which challenges the Hindu concept of *atman* (the soul or eternal self). While Hinduism holds that the *atman* is the true essence of an individual, infinite and unchanging, Buddhism teaches that there is no permanent self. According to the Buddha, what we perceive as the self is merely a collection of ever-changing physical and mental components (the five aggregates: form, sensation, perception, mental formations, and consciousness). This impermanence is a core cause of suffering (*dukkha*), and understanding the absence of a permanent self is essential to attaining Nirvana.
4. **Rejection of Vedic Rituals and Priestly Authority:** At the time of Siddhartha, Hinduism was dominated by elaborate Vedic rituals and sacrifices, often led by Brahmin priests. These rituals were necessary for maintaining cosmic order and achieving worldly success or spiritual rewards. The Buddha, however, rejected the idea that rituals or intermediaries were essential for spiritual progress. His teachings emphasised personal ethical conduct, meditation, and direct insight into the nature of reality as the means to enlightenment.
5. **The Four Noble Truths and the Eightfold Path:** Central to the Buddha's teachings are the Four Noble Truths:
 - **The truth of suffering (*dukkha*):** All beings experience suffering in various forms.
 - **The truth of the cause of suffering (*samudaya*):** The root of suffering lies in attachment, craving, and ignorance.
 - **The truth of the cessation of suffering (*nirodha*):** It is possible to end suffering by eliminating its causes.
 - **The truth of the path to the cessation of suffering (*magga*):** The Eightfold Path achieves this end.

The Eightfold Path includes right understanding, right intention, right speech, right action, right livelihood, right effort, right mindfulness, and right concentration. This ethical and philosophical guide forms the core of Buddhist practice, offering a middle way between self-indulgence and extreme asceticism.

Continuities with Hinduism

Despite its departure from Hindu orthodoxy, Buddhism remains deeply connected to many aspects of the Indian spiritual tradition.

- **Karma and Rebirth:** Buddhism and Hinduism hold that one's actions (*karma*) determine future experiences, whether in this life or the next. Both religions also accept the concept of *samsara*, the cycle of birth, death, and rebirth.
- **Meditative Practices:** Meditation, a central Buddhist practice, was already prevalent in certain Vedic traditions. Through his insights, the Buddha developed specific meditation techniques (such as *vipassana* or insight meditation) to cultivate mindfulness and wisdom.

Buddhism's Global Influence

Over time, Buddhism spread beyond India, becoming a major spiritual force in Central, East, and Southeast Asia. While it gradually declined in India, its birthplace, it flourished in countries like Sri Lanka, China, Japan, Korea, and Tibet. Each region developed its interpretation of the Buddha's teachings, leading to the formation of distinct schools, such as Theravada (The School of the Elders), Mahayana (The Great Vehicle), and Vajrayana (The Diamond Vehicle).

Judaism: A Journey to Liberation

Often regarded as the world's first major monotheistic religion, Judaism traces its origins to the ancient Near East over 4,000 years ago. The narrative begins with the patriarch Abraham, considered the father of the Jewish people, and his covenant with God (*Yahweh*). This foundational moment is believed to have occurred around 2000 BCE. However, Judaism's most formative story centres on Moses and the Exodus from Egypt, an event defining the Jewish people's identity and covenantal relationship with God.

The Covenant with Abraham: The Birth of Monotheism

The story of Judaism begins with Abraham, who lived in the ancient city of Ur in Mesopotamia (modern-day Iraq). According to Jewish tradition, God called Abraham to leave his homeland and travel to Canaan (modern-day Israel/Palestine), where he would become the father of a great nation. This covenant, or sacred agreement, established Abraham and his descendants as God's chosen people, tasked with upholding His commandments and spreading the knowledge of the one true God.

The covenant between God and Abraham significantly departs from the polytheistic beliefs that dominated the ancient world. Unlike the gods of Mesopotamia, Egypt, and other ancient civilisations, the God of Abraham was singular, omnipotent, omniscient, and deeply involved in His people's moral and ethical lives. This monotheism would become the cornerstone of the Jewish faith.

The covenant also promised that Abraham's descendants would inherit the land of Canaan and that through them, all nations of the world would be blessed. Abraham's faith and obedience are the foundation of the Jewish people's enduring relationship with God, often called the Abrahamic Covenant.

Moses and the Exodus: A Defining Moment

While Abraham's covenant established the Jewish people's unique relationship with God, the story of Moses and the Exodus solidified their identity as a nation. The Exodus is considered one of the most important narratives in Judaism, recounting the Israelites' escape from slavery in Egypt and their journey toward the Promised Land.

The Israelites had settled in Egypt during a famine, but as their numbers grew, they were eventually enslaved by the Egyptians. According to the Hebrew Bible (the *Tanakh*), Moses, born to an Israelite family but raised as a prince in the Egyptian court, was chosen by God to lead his people to freedom. After several miraculous plagues inflicted on Egypt, Pharaoh finally agreed to let the Israelites go.

The journey from Egypt, however, was challenging. The Israelites wandered in the desert for 40 years before reaching the Promised Land of Canaan. Along the way, Moses received the Ten Commandments from God at Mount Sinai, a momentous event that provided Judaism's moral and legal foundation. The Ten Commandments form the core of Jewish law, known as the *Torah*.

The Torah: The Foundation of Jewish Law

The Torah, often translated as “instruction” or “law,” is the central text of Judaism. It consists of the first five books of the Hebrew Bible—*Genesis*, *Exodus*, *Leviticus*, *Numbers*, and *Deuteronomy*—and outlines the laws and teachings that guide Jewish life. While the Ten Commandments are the most well-known part of the Torah, 613 *mitzvot* (commandments) govern every aspect of life, from ethical behaviour to religious rituals.

At the heart of the Torah is a covenantal relationship between God and the Jewish people. God is not a distant, indifferent deity but one who cares deeply about justice, morality, and the well-being of His creation. In return, the Jewish people are expected to live according to God’s laws, promoting righteousness and justice in the world.

The Torah emphasises the importance of ethical monotheism—the belief that God is one and demands ethical behaviour from His people. This ethical framework sets Judaism apart from many ancient religions, which often focused on ritual sacrifices and appeasing the gods rather than moral conduct.

The Importance of the Exodus in Jewish Identity

The Exodus story is central to Jewish religious and cultural identity. It is commemorated annually during the festival of Passover (*Pesach*), which celebrates the Israelites’ liberation from Egyptian bondage. The story of the Exodus is not just a historical event but also a powerful symbol of hope, resilience, and divine justice. Throughout Jewish history, the Exodus has been a source of inspiration during times of persecution, exile, and hardship.

The Exodus's liberation, justice, and covenant themes resonate in Jewish thought and practice. The belief that God intervenes in history to save His people from oppression has shaped Jewish understanding of their relationship with God and their mission in the world.

Monotheism and the Concept of God in Judaism

Judaism’s revolutionary contribution to religious thought is its concept of monotheism—the belief in one, all-powerful, and indivisible God. This contrasts sharply with the

polytheistic traditions of surrounding cultures, where gods were often associated with natural forces, cities, or specific peoples. In Judaism, God is the creator of the entire universe and is not limited to any geographical region or people.

Judaism also introduces the idea that God is both transcendent and immanent. He is above and beyond the physical world yet intimately involved in human affairs, guiding and shaping history. This belief is reflected in the Jewish prayer *Shema Yisrael* (“Hear, O Israel: the Lord our God, the Lord is one”), which affirms God's unity and uniqueness.

God's relationship with humanity is not one of fear or appeasement but one of love and justice. The Jewish understanding of God is deeply ethical; He is a God who demands justice, righteousness, and compassion. This ethical monotheism profoundly influenced the development of Western religious and moral thought.

Prophets and Kings: The Evolution of Jewish Faith

After the Exodus and the entry into the Promised Land, the Israelites established a kingdom under leaders like King David and Solomon. During this period, prophets were crucial in guiding and reminding the people of their covenantal obligations. Figures like Isaiah, Jeremiah, and Ezekiel called for social justice, repentance, and faithfulness to God's commandments.

The destruction of the First Temple by the Babylonians in 586 BCE and the subsequent exile of the Jewish people to Babylon were traumatic events that reshaped Jewish theology. In exile, the Jewish people deepened their commitment to the Torah and the covenant, preserving their identity despite losing their homeland.

Judaism's Lasting Legacy

Judaism's contribution to world history is immeasurable. Its monotheistic belief system laid the groundwork for Christianity and Islam, two other major world religions with the same Abrahamic roots. Judaism's ethical teachings, particularly its emphasis on justice, compassion, and the sanctity of human life have deeply influenced Western moral and legal thought.

Despite centuries of persecution and diaspora, the Jewish people have maintained their faith, culture, and traditions, remaining one of the oldest continuous religious communities in the world. Judaism's rich theological and legal traditions, its profound sense of history, and its unshakable faith in God's covenant with His people continue to inspire millions today.

Christianity: A Faith Born from Oppression

Christianity, one of the largest religions in the world today, originated in the 1st century CE in the Roman province of Judea (modern-day Israel/Palestine). The region was under Roman rule, and the Jewish population lived under harsh economic and political oppression. Within this context, Christianity arose as a movement within Judaism centred around the teachings of Jesus of Nazareth, a Jewish preacher who challenged religious authorities and Roman rule, preaching a radical message of love, forgiveness, and salvation.

The Life and Message of Jesus Christ

Jesus was born into a Jewish family, likely around 4 BCE, during the reign of King Herod the Great. His teachings, recorded in the Gospels, emphasised the coming of the Kingdom of God, a new age of justice and peace where God's will would be fully realised. He called for repentance, faith in God, and the practice of unconditional love and forgiveness toward others. These teachings struck a chord with the common people but also brought him into conflict with the Jewish religious authorities, particularly the Pharisees and Sadducees, and with Roman rulers, who saw his growing influence as a threat to their control.

One of the central aspects of Jesus' message was the idea of personal salvation and redemption through faith in God. He taught that God's love extended to all people, including the marginalised, sinners, and outcasts. He also spoke of eternal life, promising those who believed in him would enter the Kingdom of Heaven. These concepts of universal love, mercy, and salvation were revolutionary and challenged the religious practices of the time, which were often seen as legalistic and exclusive.

The Crucifixion and Resurrection

The tension between Jesus and the authorities culminated in his arrest and crucifixion, an event central to Christian belief. According to Christian doctrine, Jesus' crucifixion was not the end but a necessary sacrifice for the sins of humanity. Christians believe that three days after his death, Jesus rose from the dead—a belief known as the Resurrection. This event, as described in the Gospels, is considered the foundation of the Christian faith. It confirmed Jesus as the Messiah (the "Christ" in Greek), and his resurrection symbolised hope, victory over death, and the promise of eternal life for all believers.

The crucifixion and resurrection gave rise to the Christian belief in Jesus as the *Son of God* and the *Savior of humanity*, who had fulfilled the messianic prophecies of the

Hebrew Bible (Old Testament). The resurrection solidified the faith of Jesus' followers and set the stage for the spread of Christianity throughout the Roman Empire.

The Role of the Apostles: Spreading the Gospel

After Jesus' death and resurrection, his followers, known as apostles, began to spread his teachings. Central figures in this early Christian movement included Peter, traditionally regarded as the apostles' leader, and Paul, a former Pharisee who experienced a profound conversion and became one of Christianity's most influential missionaries.

- **Peter:** One of Jesus' closest disciples, Peter is often considered the first leader of the Christian community in Jerusalem. According to tradition, he was instrumental in spreading the message of Jesus among Jewish communities.
- **Paul:** Originally known as Saul of Tarsus, Paul was a devout Jew and a Roman citizen who initially persecuted Christians. After a dramatic vision of the risen Jesus on the road to Damascus, Paul became one of Christianity's most fervent advocates. His missionary journeys across the Roman Empire helped spread the faith to non-Jewish (Gentile) communities, particularly in cities like Corinth, Ephesus, and Rome. Paul's letters (epistles) to these early Christian communities form a significant portion of the New Testament.

The apostles emphasised Jesus' message of salvation and the belief that his death and resurrection offered redemption from sin. They travelled extensively, founding Christian communities and preaching that faith in Jesus was the path to eternal life. This missionary zeal and relative ease of travel within the Roman Empire allowed Christianity to spread rapidly beyond its Jewish roots.

The New Testament: A New Covenant

The New Testament, written by the apostles and early followers of Jesus, provides the theological and historical foundation of Christianity. While it builds on the Jewish *Tanakh* (referred to by Christians as the Old Testament), the New Testament introduces new theological concepts, such as the belief in the Trinity (Father, Son, and Holy Spirit) and the idea of a New Covenant between God and humanity, fulfilled through Jesus' life, death, and resurrection.

The New Testament consists of:

1. The Gospels (Matthew, Mark, Luke, and John) narrate Jesus's life, teachings, death, and resurrection.

2. The Acts of the Apostles detail the early Christian community and the spread of the faith after Jesus' ascension.
3. The Epistles are letters Paul and other apostles wrote to various Christian communities, offering theological guidance and moral teachings.
4. The Book of Revelation is a prophetic text that speaks of God's ultimate victory over evil and establishing a new heaven and earth.

Through these writings, Christianity preserved Jesus' teachings and developed new theological doctrines, particularly concerning salvation, grace, and the role of the Church.

Separation from Judaism

Christianity initially emerged as a Jewish sect. Jesus and his earliest followers were Jews who followed Jewish law and traditions. However, as Christianity spread among Gentile populations, particularly through the efforts of Paul, it gradually separated from its Jewish roots. One key point of division was whether Gentile converts needed to observe Jewish laws, such as circumcision and dietary restrictions. Paul argued that faith in Christ alone was sufficient for salvation and that adherence to Jewish law was no longer necessary.

This theological shift, along with increasing hostility from both Jewish and Roman authorities, led to a gradual estrangement between Christians and Jews. By the end of the 1st century CE, Christianity had developed into a distinct religion with its beliefs, practices, and community structures.

Persecution and Growth

For the first three centuries, Christianity was a minority religion often persecuted by the Roman authorities. Christians refused to participate in worshipping Roman gods and the emperor, which was seen as a threat to the stability of the Roman state. Many Christians were martyred for their faith during this period, and their courage and steadfastness in the face of persecution helped to strengthen and spread the movement.

Despite these challenges, Christianity grew, attracting converts from diverse backgrounds, including Jews and Gentiles. The message of hope, salvation, and eternal life resonated with many people living under Roman rule, particularly those marginalised by society.

The Triumph of Christianity in the Roman Empire

In the early 4th century, Christianity transformed dramatically from a persecuted faith to the dominant religion of the Roman Empire. This shift began with the conversion of Emperor Constantine the Great, who, after reportedly seeing a vision of the cross before a crucial battle, embraced Christianity and issued the Edict of Milan in 313 CE, granting religious tolerance to Christians.

Constantine's conversion and support for Christianity paved the way for spreading the faith throughout the empire. By the end of the 4th century, under Emperor Theodosius I, Christianity was declared the Roman Empire's official religion, marking a monumental turning point in its history.

The Trinity and the Development of Christian Doctrine

One of the most distinctive theological developments in Christianity is the doctrine of the Trinity, which describes God as one being in three persons: the Father, the Son (Jesus Christ), and the Holy Spirit. While this concept is not explicitly outlined in the New Testament, it was developed by early Christian theologians in response to debates about the nature of Jesus and his relationship with God.

The Council of Nicaea, convened by Constantine in 325 CE, was a landmark event in developing Christian doctrine. At this council, the Nicene Creed was formulated, affirming the belief in the Trinity and declaring that Jesus was of the same substance (*homoousios*) as God the Father. This countered the Arian heresy, which claimed that Jesus was a created being.

Islam: A New Revelation

Islam, one of the world's major monotheistic religions, was founded in the 7th century CE by the Prophet Muhammad in Mecca, located in present-day Saudi Arabia. During social, political, and spiritual turmoil, Islam emerged in a region of diverse religious beliefs, including polytheism, Christianity, Judaism, and Zoroastrianism. The Arabian Peninsula was a trade centre, and Mecca was an important religious site, with the Kaaba, a sanctuary housing numerous deities worshipped by the local tribes.

Muhammad's prophetic mission began within this context, forming a new religious and political community that would profoundly influence world history.

The Early Life of Muhammad

Muhammad was born around 570 CE into the Quraysh tribe, the ruling tribe of Mecca. He was orphaned at a young age and was raised by his uncle, Abu Talib. Growing up, Muhammad gained a reputation for his honesty and trustworthiness, earning him the nickname *Al-Amin* (the trustworthy). As a young man, he worked as a merchant, and through his trade, he met Jews, Christians, and other religious groups, which likely influenced his spiritual development.

At 25, Muhammad married Khadija, a wealthy widow who supported him throughout the early years of his prophetic mission. Despite his success as a merchant, Muhammad was deeply troubled by the social inequalities, tribal conflicts, and moral decay he witnessed in Meccan society. He often retreated to the cave of Hira in the mountains surrounding Mecca to meditate and seek spiritual guidance.

Muhammad's First Revelation

At 40, during one of these retreats, Muhammad received his first revelation from the angel Gabriel (*Jibril* in Arabic). This event, known as the *Laylat al-Qadr* (the Night of Power), marked the beginning of Muhammad's prophetic career. Gabriel revealed to Muhammad the words of God, which he was instructed to recite. These revelations continued for the next 23 years of Muhammad's life, forming the basis of the Quran, Islam's holy book.

The first revealed verses emphasised the oneness of God (*Allah*) and called on Muhammad to spread the message of monotheism, righteousness, and social justice. Muhammad's message challenged the polytheistic practices of the Quraysh, who were deeply invested in idol worship centred around the Kaaba.

The Message of Islam: Tawhid and Submission to God

At the heart of Islam is the concept of *tawhid*, or the absolute oneness of God. Islam teaches that God is the sole creator and sustainer of the universe and merciful, all-knowing, and all-powerful. The term “Islam” itself means “submission” or “surrender” to the will of God, and a Muslim submits to God’s divine will.

Muhammad’s early teachings focused on recognising God’s unity and living a life of moral integrity, justice, and compassion. Islam also introduced the concept of the *umma*, or the global Muslim community, united by faith in the one God. The *Five Pillars of Islam* are key to Islamic belief, which outline the essential acts of worship and devotion that every Muslim must follow.

1. **Shahada** (Faith): The declaration of faith, stating that there is no god but God (*Allah*) and Muhammad is His messenger.
2. **Salat** (Prayer): The performance of five daily prayers facing Mecca.
3. **Zakat** (Charity): Giving alms to the poor and needy, emphasising social justice and the equitable distribution of wealth.
4. **Sawm** (Fasting): Observing the fast during Ramadan, a time of self-discipline and reflection.
5. **Hajj** (Pilgrimage): The pilgrimage to Mecca, which every Muslim must undertake at least once in their lifetime if able.

These pillars define Islam's spiritual practices and emphasise the importance of community, charity, and submission to God’s will.

The Quran: The Holy Book of Islam

The Quran, regarded by Muslims as the literal word of God, was revealed to Muhammad over 23 years ago and compiled into its current form shortly after his death. It is the ultimate guide for Muslims, providing instructions on faith, morality, law, and personal conduct. It addresses various topics, from God's nature and the universe's creation to family life, social justice, and governance.

Unlike the Jewish and Christian scriptures, which evolved over centuries, the Quran is believed to be the unaltered and final revelation of God’s will, preserved in its original Arabic form. Muslims consider it the definitive and complete guide for human life, superseding earlier revelations from prophets like Abraham, Moses, and Jesus.

Islam's Relationship with Judaism and Christianity

Islam shares many foundational beliefs and stories with Judaism and Christianity. Muslims revere figures such as Abraham (*Ibrahim*), Moses (*Musa*), and Jesus (*Isa*) as prophets who conveyed God's message to humanity. Islam regards itself as the continuation and completion of the monotheistic tradition, with Muhammad as the final prophet (*Khatam an-Nabiyyin*), bringing God's ultimate and most complete revelation.

While Islam acknowledges the importance of the Torah and the Gospels, Muslims believe that these earlier scriptures were altered or misunderstood over time. The Quran, therefore, is seen as the correction and completion of God's guidance, restoring the true message of monotheism. In Islamic theology, both Jews and Christians are considered "People of the Book" (*Ahl al-Kitab*), and they are accorded a special status in Islamic law, though their scriptures are seen as incomplete.

The Hijra: Migration to Medina and the Birth of the Islamic State

As Muhammad's message gained followers in Mecca, it also attracted increasing hostility from the Quraysh, who saw his monotheistic preaching as a threat to their political and economic interests. In 622 CE, facing persecution, Muhammad and his followers fled to the city of Yathrib (later renamed Medina), an event known as the *Hijra*. This migration marks the beginning of the Islamic calendar and the establishment of the first Muslim community under Muhammad's leadership.

Muhammad acted as a spiritual, political, and military leader in Medina. He established the Constitution of Medina, which created a framework for peaceful coexistence among the city's diverse population, including Muslims, Jews, and pagan tribes. This document is one of the earliest examples of a pluralistic society governed by Islamic principles of justice and fairness.

The Expansion of Islam: Challenges and Triumphs

In the years following the Hijra, Islam rapidly expanded throughout the Arabian Peninsula. Muhammad and his followers faced several military challenges, including conflicts with the Quraysh and other tribes. Notable battles, such as the Battle of Badr and the Battle of Uhud, played a significant role in consolidating Muslim power.

In 630 CE, Muhammad and his followers returned to Mecca and peacefully conquered the city. Upon entering the Kaaba, Muhammad cleansed it of its idols and rededicated it to worship the one true God, Allah. This act symbolised the triumph of monotheism over polytheism in Arabia.

By Muhammad's death in 632 CE, Islam had spread throughout most of the Arabian Peninsula, and its influence was beginning to extend beyond. The rapid expansion of Islam in the decades following Muhammad's death can be attributed to a combination of factors, including the appeal of its message, the administrative and military prowess of early Muslim leaders, and the political instability of the neighbouring Byzantine and Sassanian empires.

The Caliphate and the Spread of Islam

After Muhammad's death, the Muslim community faced the challenge of succession. The title of *caliph* (successor) was given to Abu Bakr, one of Muhammad's closest companions, and under his leadership, the caliphate expanded beyond the Arabian Peninsula. The early caliphs, known as the *Rashidun* (rightly guided) caliphs, continued to spread Islam through conquest and diplomacy, extending Muslim rule into the Levant, Persia, Egypt, and North Africa.

The spread of Islam was not merely a result of military conquests; it was also facilitated by trade, missionary efforts, and the appeal of its message of equality and justice. Many regions under Muslim rule, particularly in North Africa and the Middle East, gradually converted to Islam over the centuries, drawn by its emphasis on social justice, the equality of all believers, and the simplicity of its monotheistic creed.

The Legacy of Islam

One of the most remarkable phenomena in history is Islam's rapid rise from a small religious movement in 7th-century Arabia to a major world religion within a century. Today, Islam is the second-largest religion in the world, with over 1.8 billion followers. Its teachings continue to shape the lives of millions of people, influencing religious practices, law, culture, and politics in Muslim-majority societies.

Central to Islam's lasting influence is its ability to adapt to diverse cultural contexts while maintaining its core message of *tawhid* (the oneness of God) and *submission to God's will*. As the final revelation, the Quran remains the guiding text for Muslims, offering spiritual, moral, and legal guidance for individuals and communities.

Sikhism: A Synthesis of Hinduism and Islam

Sikhism, one of the youngest major world religions, was founded in the late 15th century in the Punjab region of India by Guru Nanak. Its emergence occurred in a period marked by social, religious, and political strife. The area, then under the rule of the Mughal Empire, witnessed tensions between the Hindu majority and the ruling Muslim elite, each practising distinct religious traditions. In this context, Guru Nanak's teachings offered a new spiritual path, promoting devotion to one God, equality, and the rejection of rigid social hierarchies and rituals.

Sikhism developed as a distinct religion that drew on elements from both Hindu and Islamic traditions but ultimately forged a unique identity. Over time, the teachings of Guru Nanak were consolidated and expanded by subsequent Sikh Gurus, most notably Guru Gobind Singh, who established the Khalsa, the community of committed Sikhs, and institutionalised the faith.

The Life and Teachings of Guru Nanak

Guru Nanak, the founder of Sikhism, was born in 1469 CE in a small village called Talwandi (now Nankana Sahib in modern-day Pakistan). From a young age, Nanak demonstrated a deep spiritual inclination, questioning the prevailing religious practices and social injustices around him. He rejected the ritualism and formalism in Hinduism and Islam and sought a direct connection with the divine.

At 30, Guru Nanak experienced a profound spiritual revelation, after which he began travelling across India and beyond, spreading his message. His teachings focused on the oneness of God (*Ik Onkar*), the equality of all human beings, and the importance of leading a life of truth, compassion, and humility. He emphasised that true spirituality lay not in religious rituals but in devotion to God, ethical conduct, and service to others.

One of Guru Nanak's key messages was rejecting the caste system, which had become deeply entrenched in Hindu society. He preached that all humans are equal in the eyes of God, regardless of their caste, creed, or gender. This belief in social equality was revolutionary then and became a core tenet of Sikhism.

Key Beliefs of Sikhism

Sikhism is a monotheistic faith that believes in one, formless, and all-pervading God. The primary scripture of Sikhism, the *Guru Granth Sahib*, emphasises devotion to God, righteous living, and pursuing spiritual wisdom. Some of the core beliefs and principles of Sikhism include the following.

1. **Oneness of God (*Ik Onkar*):** Sikhism teaches that only one God is the same for all people, regardless of their religion or background. This God is formless, timeless, transcendent, and immanent, present in all creation.
2. **Equality and Social Justice:** Guru Nanak rejected the hierarchical structures of caste, class, and gender. He taught everyone to be treated with respect and dignity regardless of social status. Sikhism advocates for social justice and the fair treatment of all individuals.
3. **Rejection of Ritualism:** Sikhism is critical of empty rituals and superstitions found in both Hinduism and Islam. Guru Nanak emphasised inner devotion, ethical living, and remembrance of God through meditation (*Naam Simran*) rather than ritualistic practices.
4. **The Three Pillars of Sikhism:** Guru Nanak's teachings revolve around three central practices.
 - **Naam Japna:** Meditating on God's name.
 - **Kirat Karni:** Earning an honest living through hard work and righteous means.
 - **Vand Chakna:** Sharing with others, especially those in need, and practising charity.
5. **The Importance of Community Service (Seva):** Sikhs are encouraged to engage in selfless service to the community, reflecting the importance of humility and compassion in their faith. This principle is embodied in the practice of Langar, the community kitchen where free meals are served to people of all backgrounds, a practice started by Guru Nanak.

The Sikh Gurus: Shaping the Religion

After Guru Nanak died in 1539, his spiritual and leadership role was passed on to nine successive Gurus, each of whom contributed to the growth and development of Sikhism. These Gurus guided the Sikh community and elaborated on Guru Nanak's teachings.

- **Guru Angad (1504–1552):** The second Guru, Guru Angad, institutionalised the *Gurmukhi* script, which became the standard for writing the Punjabi language. This helped preserve the teachings of Guru Nanak in written form.
- **Guru Amar Das (1479–1574):** The third Guru emphasised social equality, particularly women's rights. He established *Manji* and *Piri*, systems of community governance that empowered women to lead religious gatherings.
- **Guru Ram Das (1534–1581):** The fourth Guru founded the city of Amritsar, which became the spiritual and cultural centre of Sikhism.
- **Guru Arjan (1563–1606):** The fifth Guru compiled the *Adi Granth*, the precursor to the *Guru Granth Sahib*, and oversaw the construction of the

Harmandir Sahib (Golden Temple) in Amritsar, the holiest shrine in Sikhism. Guru Arjan was executed by Mughal authorities, marking the beginning of Sikh persecution under Mughal rule.

- **Guru Hargobind (1595–1644):** The sixth Guru adopted a more militant stance in response to Mughal aggression. He emphasised the importance of defending the faith and introduced the concept of *Miri* and *Piri*, symbolised by two swords, representing temporal and spiritual authority.
- **Guru Tegh Bahadur (1621–1675):** The ninth Guru is remembered for his martyrdom defending religious freedom. He was executed by Mughal Emperor Aurangzeb for resisting forced conversions of Hindus to Islam, further solidifying Sikhism's stance against religious persecution.

The Formation of the Khalsa: Guru Gobind Singh's Legacy

Guru Gobind Singh, the tenth and final human Guru, played a pivotal role in shaping Sikhism as it exists today. Born in 1666, Guru Gobind Singh faced increasing persecution from the Mughal authorities. In response to these challenges, he established the *Khalsa* in 1699, a community of initiated Sikhs who were committed to defending their faith and living by the highest moral standards.

The Khalsa was created during the festival of *Vaisakhi* when Guru Gobind Singh called on Sikhs to come forward and offer their lives for their faith. Five Sikhs stepped forward, and they became the first members of the Khalsa, known as the *Panj Pyare* (the Five Beloved Ones). They were initiated through a ceremony involving the preparation and drinking of *Amrit* (sugar water), symbolising spiritual rebirth.

The creation of the Khalsa transformed Sikhism into a more organised and militant community, ready to defend itself against external threats. Members of the Khalsa were given a distinct identity, marked by the *Five Ks*.

1. **Kesh:** Uncut hair, symbolising spirituality and respect for God's creation.
2. **Kanga:** A wooden comb representing cleanliness and discipline.
3. **Kara:** A steel bracelet that signifies unity with God and the Sikh community.
4. **Kachera:** Cotton undergarments symbolising modesty and self-control.
5. **Kirpan:** A ceremonial sword representing the Sikh's duty to protect the weak and uphold justice.

In addition to founding the Khalsa, Guru Gobind Singh declared that after his death, the Sikh community would no longer have a human Guru. Instead, the *Guru Granth Sahib*, the Sikh holy scripture, would serve as the eternal Guru, and the Khalsa would act as the temporal and spiritual leader of the Sikh people.

Sikhism's Distinct Identity

While Sikhism incorporates elements from Hinduism and Islam, it is a distinct religion with its own theological, ethical, and social framework. Unlike Hinduism, Sikhism rejects the caste system and idol worship. Unlike Islam, Sikhism does not practice circumcision or endorse a fixed legal code like Sharia. Instead, Sikhism offers a spiritual path focused on worshipping one formless God, ethical living, and pursuing justice and equality.

The unique blend of Hindu and Islamic elements, combined with the leadership of the Sikh Gurus, shaped Sikhism into a distinct faith that promotes a just and egalitarian society. Its emphasis on the oneness of God, rejection of social hierarchies, and dedication to community service set it apart as a religion that advocates both spiritual and social transformation.

Hinduism: The World's Oldest Religion

Unlike the other major world religions, Hinduism has no single founder or specific moment of origin. Instead, it is a vast, diverse, and evolving religious tradition developed over millennia in the Indian subcontinent. It is often described as *Sanatana Dharma*, meaning “the eternal way” or “the eternal order,” reflecting its spiritual teachings’ timeless and enduring nature. Hinduism is the oldest living religion, with roots stretching over 9,000 years, making it one of the world’s most ancient belief systems.

The Origins of Hinduism: The Vedic Period

The earliest roots of Hinduism can be traced to the Vedic period, which began around 9000 years ago. During this time, the sacred texts known as the Vedas were composed, marking the beginning of Hindu thought. The Vedas—*Rigveda*, *Samaveda*, *Yajurveda*, and *Atharvaveda*—are considered the foundational texts of Hinduism and are regarded as *Shrutis* (“that which is heard”), believed to have been divinely revealed to ancient sages, known as *rishis*.

The Vedas contain hymns, prayers, rituals, and philosophical discussions centred on cosmology, nature, and the nature of existence. The primary focus of early Vedic religion was the worship of natural forces and deities, such as *Agni* (fire), *Indra* (the king of the gods), and *Surya* (the sun). These deities were invoked through complex rituals and sacrifices (*yajna*) conducted by priests (*Brahmins*), who played a crucial role in mediating between humans and the divine.

Over time, the Vedic tradition gave rise to various philosophical and religious ideas that became integral to Hinduism. As the Vedic corpus expanded, so did its interpretations, leading to multiple schools of thought and practices.

The Upanishads and the Rise of Philosophical Hinduism

Around 800-500 BCE, a body of spiritual texts known as the Upanishads emerged. These texts represent the philosophical culmination of the Vedic tradition and mark a shift from ritualistic worship to reflective and meditative practices. The Upanishads focus on understanding the nature of the self (*atman*), the ultimate reality (*Brahman*), and the relationship between the two. One of the key teachings of the Upanishads is that the individual soul (*atman*) is identical to the universal soul (*Brahman*), which is the source of all existence.

The Upanishads also introduced concepts such as *karma* (the law of moral causation), *samsara* (the cycle of birth, death, and rebirth), and *moksha* (liberation from the cycle of

rebirth). These ideas would become central to Hindu philosophy and practice, shaping how Hindus understood their place in the universe and their spiritual goals.

The Upanishadic teachings emphasised personal introspection and spiritual knowledge over ritualism. This philosophical tradition laid the groundwork for later developments in Hindu thought, including the six classical schools of Hindu philosophy (*Shad Darshanas*), which include:

1. **Sankhya:** A dualistic philosophy distinguishing between matter (*Prakriti*) and consciousness (*Purusha*).
2. **Yoga:** A spiritual and physical practice that seeks to control the mind and senses, leading to liberation.
3. **Nyaya:** A school focused on logic and epistemology.
4. **Vaisheshika:** A system that explores the nature of reality through atomistic theory.
5. **Mimamsa:** A school that emphasises the importance of Vedic rituals and ethics.
6. **Vedanta:** A non-dualistic philosophy that teaches the unity of *Atman* and *Brahman*.

The Epics and Puranas: Shaping Hindu History and Practice

Alongside the Upanishads' philosophical developments, Hinduism evolved through its rich history, preserved in two of India's greatest epics: the Mahabharata, the *Ramayana*, and the *Puranas*.

- The Mahabharata, composed between the 4th century BCE and the 4th century CE, is an epic narrative about the Kurukshetra War and the moral dilemmas the characters involved face. Within the Mahabharata is the *Bhagavad Gita*, a text of immense spiritual significance, in which the god Krishna instructs the warrior Arjuna on duty, devotion, and the nature of reality. The *Bhagavad Gita* has become one of the most revered texts in Hinduism. She addresses key issues such as the path to liberation through devotion (*bhakti*), knowledge (*jnana*), and selfless action (*karma yoga*).
- Traditionally attributed to the sage Valmiki, the *Ramayana* tells the story of Prince Rama's quest to rescue his wife, Sita, from the demon king Ravana. The *Ramayana* explores themes of duty, righteousness, and the ideal relationship between individuals and society. Like the Mahabharata, the *Ramayana* has shaped Hindu values and ethical conduct.
- The *Puranas*, composed between the 3rd and 10th centuries CE, provide many legends, and genealogies of gods, sages, and kings. They introduce the pantheon of Hindu deities—such as Vishnu, Shiva, and Devi—and their

various incarnations and manifestations. The Puranas also emphasise devotional worship (*bhakti*), which became a major focus of Hindu practice in the medieval period.

Hindu Practices: Worship, Rituals, and the Pursuit of Moksha

Hinduism encompasses various religious practices, rituals, and forms of worship. These practices often vary depending on regional traditions, sects, and communities but share certain common elements. One of the defining features of Hinduism is its pluralistic nature, which allows for a diversity of paths to spiritual fulfilment.

- **Deity Worship (*Puja*):** Hindus worship many deities, who are seen as manifestations of the one ultimate reality (*Brahman*). Major deities include Vishnu (the preserver), Shiva (the destroyer), and Devi (the goddess or divine feminine). Worship often involves offering flowers, food, and prayers at home altars or temples. Temples are central to Hindu religious life, serving as places of community gathering and spiritual devotion.
- **Meditation and Yoga:** Meditation is a key practice in Hinduism, aimed at calming the mind and realising the true nature of the self. *Yoga*, in its many forms, is a spiritual discipline that includes physical postures, breath control, and meditation, all designed to lead the practitioner toward self-realisation and liberation (*moksha*).
- **Rituals and Festivals:** Hindu rituals are diverse and often tied to key life events, such as birth, marriage, and death. They are also closely associated with the changing seasons and the lunar calendar. Major Hindu festivals include the following.
 - **Diwali:** The festival of lights, celebrating the victory of light over darkness.
 - **Holi:** The festival of colours, celebrating the arrival of spring and the triumph of good over evil.
 - **Navaratri:** A nine-night festival dedicated to the worship of the goddess Durga.
 - **Maha Shivaratri:** A night dedicated to the worship of Lord Shiva.
- **Pursuit of Moksha:** Hindu life aims to achieve moksha, or liberation from the cycle of samsara (rebirth). This can be attained through various paths, including the following.
 - **Karma Yoga:** The path of selfless action, where one performs duties without attachment to the fruits of their labour.
 - **Bhakti Yoga:** The path of devotion, one surrenders to a personal deity and seeks divine grace.

- **Jnana Yoga:** The path of knowledge, where one seeks to understand the nature of the self and its unity with Brahman.

Hindu Texts: A Wealth of Spiritual Wisdom

Hinduism's flexibility and ability to absorb and adapt to various cultural and philosophical influences can be attributed to its vast body of sacred texts. The primary texts of Hinduism are divided into two categories.

- **Shruti (That Which Is Heard):** This includes the Vedas and the Upanishads, considered divinely revealed. The Vedas are the oldest and most authoritative scriptures, while the Upanishads offer deep philosophical reflections on the nature of existence.
- **Smriti (That Which Is Remembered):** This includes the epics (*Mahabharata* and *Ramayana*), the Puranas, and the *Dharma Shastras* (legal and ethical treatises). These texts guide righteous living and are the foundation of Hindu law and ethics.

Diversity in Hinduism: Schools, Sects, and Philosophies

Hinduism is not a monolithic tradition but a collection of diverse sects, schools of thought, and philosophical traditions. This diversity allows Hindus to practice their faith differently, depending on their inclinations, family traditions, and regional customs.

- **Vaishnavism:** The worship of Vishnu and his avatars, such as Krishna and Rama.
- **Shaivism:** Shiva's worship represents both destruction and regeneration.
- **Shaktism:** Worshipping *Shakti*, the divine feminine power or goddess. Followers of Shaktism revere the goddesses Durga, Kali, Lakshmi, and Saraswati, who are seen as manifestations of the supreme cosmic force. Shaktism emphasizes the importance of feminine energy in the cosmic balance.
- **Smartism:** A more philosophical and inclusive sect that reveres five deities—Vishnu, Shiva, Shakti, Ganesha, and Surya (the sun god)—as manifestations of the same divine reality, *Brahman*. This sect allows for worshipping multiple gods but upholds the idea that all paths lead to the same ultimate truth.

Philosophical Pluralism in Hinduism

Hinduism's strength lies in its philosophical pluralism. Different schools of thought within Hinduism provide various ways of understanding the nature of reality, the self, and the divine. Individuals can pursue a path that resonates most with their beliefs and spiritual goals. While the schools differ in their interpretations, they all share karma, *dharma* (duty), and *moksha* (liberation) concepts.

- **Non-Dualism (Advaita Vedanta):** One of the most influential schools of thought in Hinduism is *Advaita Vedanta*, which teaches that the individual self (*atman*) and the ultimate reality (*Brahman*) are the same. According to this philosophy, the world of diversity and difference is an illusion (*Maya*), and human life aims to realise the underlying unity of all existence. This school was popularised by the philosopher Adi Shankaracharya in the 8th century CE.
- **Dualism (Dvaita):** In contrast to Advaita Vedanta, the *Dvaita* (dualistic) school, championed by the philosopher Madhvacharya, posits that God (*Vishnu*) and the individual soul are eternally distinct. In Dvaita, God is a personal being with whom individuals have a loving relationship, and liberation is achieved through devotion to Him.
- **Qualified Non-Dualism (Vishishtadvaita):** This school, founded by the philosopher Ramanuja, teaches that while *Atman* and *Brahman* are connected, they are not identical. God is seen as both the creator and sustainer of the universe and the individual soul retains its distinctiveness even in union with God.

These schools of thought reflect the rich diversity within Hindu philosophy and the multiple paths for seeking truth and liberation.

Hinduism's Flexibility and Absorption of Cultural Influences

One of Hinduism's hallmarks is its remarkable ability to absorb and adapt to various cultural, philosophical, and religious influences throughout history. Over the centuries, Hinduism has evolved by incorporating elements from different traditions while maintaining its core spiritual teachings.

- **Influence of Buddhism and Jainism:** Buddhism and Jainism emerged as critiques of early Hinduism's ritualistic and caste-based practices in ancient India. While these religions introduced new ideas, such as non-violence (*ahimsa*) and renunciation, Hinduism absorbed many ethical teachings. By medieval India, Hinduism had re-emphasized devotional

worship (*bhakti*) and meditation as key spiritual practices, drawing inspiration from Buddhist and Jain traditions.

- **Medieval Bhakti Movement:** The *Bhakti* movement flourished in medieval India and was a holy response to the rigidities of caste and ritualism. Saints like Ramanuja, Kabir, Tulsidas, and Mirabai popularised the worship of personal deities like Vishnu, Shiva, and the goddess. They taught that love and devotion to God were more important than caste distinctions or elaborate rituals. The Bhakti movement democratised religious practices, making them accessible to everyone regardless of caste or gender.
- **Islamic Influence:** During the medieval period, when Muslim dynasties ruled large parts of India, Hinduism interacted with Islam. Although the two religions remained distinct, Sufi mysticism and devotional practices influenced the Bhakti movement, and a cultural exchange enriched both traditions.
- **Modern Influences:** Hinduism has continued to evolve in the contemporary era, interacting with Western philosophical and scientific ideas. Reform movements like those led by Swami Vivekananda and Sri Aurobindo have emphasised social justice, non-violence, and spiritual universalism, presenting Hinduism as a progressive and dynamic tradition.

Hinduism in the Modern World

Hinduism remains a major world religion, with over a billion followers, primarily in India and Nepal. Hindu communities can also be found across the globe, particularly in countries with large Indian diasporas, such as the United States, Canada, the United Kingdom, and South Africa.

Hinduism continues to evolve in the modern world while preserving its ancient traditions. Festivals, pilgrimages, and temple worship remain central to Hindu religious life, while philosophical inquiry, yoga, and meditation are increasingly popular within and outside Hinduism. Hindu ideas, particularly those related to non-violence, self-realisation, and the unity of all beings, have profoundly influenced global spiritual and philosophical thought.

Conclusion

The origins of the world's major religions provide invaluable insights into how humanity has sought to understand existence, morality, and the divine across different cultural and historical landscapes. Each religion—Buddhism, Judaism, Christianity, Islam, Sikhism, and Hinduism—emerged in response to specific social, political, and spiritual needs of their time. Yet, they all continue to shape the modern world profoundly. Their teachings, moral frameworks, and rituals have provided spiritual guidance and influenced the development of legal systems, human rights, and ethical governance in many parts of the world.

In the contemporary global order, these religions play a vital role in maintaining cultural identity and social cohesion while fostering interfaith dialogues to promote peace and understanding in an increasingly interconnected world. As globalisation brings diverse communities into closer contact, the teachings of these religions on compassion, justice, and coexistence remain highly relevant, offering paths to mitigate conflicts and build inclusive societies.

Moreover, these religious traditions' values of equality, social justice, and the pursuit of truth resonate with many modern movements for human rights, environmental sustainability, and social equity. From Buddhism's focus on ending suffering and promoting mindfulness to Islam's emphasis on social justice and Sikhism's advocacy for equality, these teachings offer practical wisdom for addressing some of the most pressing issues of the 21st century, such as inequality, climate change, and conflict resolution.

In essence, the continued relevance of these religions in the modern world order reflects their enduring ability to adapt and provide meaning to human life. They help billions of people navigate the complexities of existence while fostering hope for a just and harmonious world.

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